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SPATIAL DISTRIBUTION OF SOME FERTILITY ELEMENTS IN SOME NORTHERN IRAQI SOILS USING GEOMATIC TECHNIQUES (REMOTE SENSING)

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Abstract

Twenty soil surface samples were collected to assess on a wide scale, the spatial distribution of soil properties including fertility ones. Where N P K were measured and spatially distributed. The least soil property variation in north of Iraq were soil pH, organic matter, and electrical conductivity where these properties are affected by the climatic conditions and zonal distribution of these features. Cation exchange capacity was correlated to clay content. Available nitrogen and phosphorus showed somewhat low content in soil while potassium showed high content in general and where also corresponded to the content of finer and coarser fraction of soil separates.

Keywords: spatial variability, N P K distribution, geotechnologies,

Introduction

Interest in lands and their fertility asset is increasing nowadays, where it's been very obvious that soil is the first natural resource that supports life for human beings (Foster and Magdoff 1998, Abbott and Murphy 2007). Therefore, many practices are applied in the field of soil fertility to increase the essential nutrients for plant growth (Sanginga and Woomer 2009, Altieri and Nicholls 2003, Mapfumo and Giller 2001). It is not easy to define soil fertility, because in fact it is a complicated definition that is affected by different external and internal factors (Jonson *et al.*, 1997, Doran *et al.*, 1999). Precipitation and temperature are affecting soil properties and fertility because it allows the potential properties to proceed in chemical and biological reactions that increase with the increase of both water and temperature (Franzluebbers 2002, Suseela *et al.*, 2012, Alvarez and Lavado 1998). Also the main soil properties themselves are affecting the soil fertility properties (Alban 1982, Soltanpour and Schwab 1977) where cation exchange capacity is affecting soil content of nutrient for example (Moore 1980, Sharma *et al.*, 2008, Bernal *et al.*, 1993). Different internal factors are participating to affect the fertility characteristics of soil such as physical properties, aeration, soil depth, topography, biological activities, water availability and many other properties (Havlin *et al.*, 2016, Gray 2005, Scoones and Toulmin 1998). Thus, soil fertility is divided to three parts, physical fertility, chemical fertility and biological fertility, where each property affects soil fertility in a different way (Almawsili 2018). Where these properties (Physical, chemical and biological) are formed due to different factors and processes (Yaalon 1975, Jenny 1994, Voroney 2007) and they show variation in their spatial distribution (Nielsen *et al.*, 1973, Mulla and McBratney 2002, Ettema and Wardle 2002).

Moreover, soil properties are variable along soil-scape and they are very difficult to be measured in the whole area of any study, therefore, the term spatial variability of soil properties arise and allows us to find an approach to determine soil properties and collecting samples for better management of soil (Soulie *et al.*, 1990; Wheib, 1997; Wheib, 2002; Iqbal *et al.*, 2005; Muzuku *et al.*, 2005 and Suliman, 2014). This study aims to determine the spatial distribution and variability of some soil properties including

some fertility properties and expressing these properties using geotechnological approach.

Materials and Methods

Area of study

The area of study was representing the northern of Iraq namely Kurdistan area where 20 surface samples were randomly collected from Erbil, Suleimaniya, and Duhok. These samples were collected and GPS reading was recorded for each location. Figure (1) shows the distribution of soil samples locations.

Fig. 1 : Study area and soil samples locations

Samples were collected in locked plastic bags and transferred for lab analysis.

Lab measures:

Physical properties:

Where particle size distribution was measured due to Day 1965.

Chemical properties:

- Electrical Conductivity EC was determined due to Richards 1954.

- pH was determined due to Richards 1954.
- Cation Exchange Capacity CEC was calculated due to Hesse 1971.
- Total Carbonate measured using calcimeter method described in Hesse 1971.
- Organic Matter OM was measured due to Walkly Black method described in Hesse 1971.

Fertility macro nutrients:

- Available Nitrogen was determined due to micro-Kjeldahl method that permits the available nitrogen to be precisely determined in the soil (Page 1982).
- Available Phosphorous was determined due to the method described in Jackson 1958.
- Available Potassium was determined using the method described in Black 1965.

Map preparations and geo-statistical analysis:

Arc GIS 10.3 for desktop was used to prepare maps of spatial distribution and variability of soil properties. Data of soil properties were kregged following the geostatistical analysis of ArcMap extensions. Resulted maps were used to show the variation in soil properties, and a general linear regression model was built for the spatial variogram shown in these maps (ESRI 2014).

Results and Discussion

Soil Chemical Properties

Table 1 shows chemical properties of the selected soils. Soil pH was ranging from 7.4-8.4. Where generally we can see that the lower pH values of soil existed in soils with higher electrical conductivity of soil extract and that is

parallel to what Miller and Kissal2010, Chorom and Rengassamy 1997, and Brady and Weil 2008 found. Also the highest value of pH was related to higher content of organic matter, and that was also corresponded to what Suave *et al.*, 1998, You *et al.*, 1999 and Curtin et al 1998 found when they studied the relationship between soil organic matter and potential of hydrogen in soil.

Electrical conductivity was ranging from 0.58 to 20.70 dS.m⁻¹ but generally most of the soils were having a low content of salts due to the low value of the electrical conductivity of soil extract, where most of soil salinity classes were under the none saline to slightly saline soils (see figure)

Organic Matter was also showing different spectrum of organic accumulations in soil, from low content of organic matter to significant content of it. OM ranged from 0.21-2.92 gm.kg⁻¹ the higher content of organic matter was spatially distributed in a partially higher precipitation and lower degrees of temperature areas. It is considerable that most of these soils are representing a mollisols and entisols, where these soils considered having a relatively higher content of organic matter that other soil in Iraq as a basic part of their classification (Soil Survey Staff 1996).

Carbonate equivalent has ranged from 10.1-42.5 gm.kg⁻¹ in the tested soil samples. There was a general significant trend of soil content of organic matter and carbonate equivalent where the highest content of organic matter affected the content of total carbonate minerals in soil, and that could be related to the value of pH that is decreased due to organic matter accumulation where more acidity leads to less carbonate accumulation (Kove and Oschiles 2012, Wang *et al.*, 2015).

Table 1: Chemical properties of soils of study

Sample No	pH	ECe dS.m	Available/ mg.kg ⁻¹			OM Kg.kg ⁻¹	CaCO ₃ Kg.kg ⁻¹	CEC Cmolc.kg ⁻¹
			N	P	K			
1	7.4	2.18	33.5	10.2	185	0.21	32.0	31.0
2	8.3	0.58	45.8	19.6	156	0.70	32.0	7.4
3	7.4	1.64	116.8	16.7	136	2.92	32.0	8.02
4	7.6	4.96	89.5	11.5	164	1.47	30.0	3.74
5	8.0	1.18	73.8	13.2	251	1.09	25.5	16.05
6	7.9	1.84	77.8	16.9	127	1.31	42.5	10.70
7	8.0	1.86	80.1	14.0	191	1.65	24.0	10.70
8	7.8	4.96	40.6	8.6	110	0.40	31.5	18.72
9	7.7	8.68	39.8	13.4	206	0.60	28.0	5.35
10	7.7	5.16	29.8	13.6	150	0.43	29.5	8.02
11	8.1	1.81	81.7	22.1	242	1.84	10.1	32.8
12	8.0	21.6	73.5	14.5	235	0.87	29.5	12.3
13	7.9	20.70	33.8	7.5	187	0.30	30.0	18.72
14	8.4	2.80	119.1	22.3	110	2.86	11.0	27.45
15	8.3	3.62	95.6	30.0	312	1.52	27.5	37.7
16	8.2	1.24	44.1	17.5	538	0.42	21.5	26.75
17	8.3	1.94	63.9	9.2	398	1.31	32.5	33.87
18	7.4	8.42	69.6	14.2	246	0.87	24.0	34.77
19	8.3	1.00	84.9	10.5	383	1.68	17.5	32.10
20	8.0	2.80	70.5	12.4	286	1.05	16.8	27.82

Cation exchange capacity was generally high. It ranged between 3.74-34.10 Cmolc.kg⁻¹. Where the highest value of this characteristic was related to clay content in soil. It was

related to the content of the finer or coarser particles in soil as we can see that the finer soil textures have higher cation exchange capacity as shown in table 2.

Table 2 : Particle size distribution and texture of the studied soils

Sample No	Clay	Silt	Sand	Soil texture
	gm.kg ⁻¹			
1	31.2	52.4	16.4	SiCL
2	15.7	45.5	38.8	L
3	17.6	42.3	40.1	L
4	9.5	23.9	66.6	SL
5	25.2	56.0	18.8	SiL
6	18.6	56.9	24.5	SiL
7	14.5	59	26.5	SiL
8	30.8	52.4	16.8	SiCL
9	42.5	49.1	8.4	SiC
10	20.4	57.1	22.5	SiL
11	33.8	50.4	15.8	SiCL
12	20.8	60.6	18.6	SiL
13	27.6	54.1	18.3	SiCL
14	25.8	53.7	20.5	SiL
15	44.5	48.8	6.7	SiC
16	26.6	53.3	20.1	SiL
17	38.8	42.4	18.8	SiCL
18	40.8	43.6	15.6	SiC
19	30.5	53.6	15.9	SiCL
20	30.7	56.6	12.7	SiCL

From table 2, we can see that soil texture was generally ranging from medium texture to fine texture except some sites were coarse textured the matter that led to low cation exchange capacity as mentioned above. Clay content was ranging from 9.5 gm.kg⁻¹ to 44.5 gm.kg⁻¹ of a sandy loam to silty clay soil textures respectively. The variation in clay content will definitely cause variation in other separates. The finer separate was correlated to the exchange capacity and organic matter and that is related to the high surfaces area of the organic matter which increases the soil surfaces in return, thus it increases the exchange capacity (Tiessen and Stewart 1981, Wang and Keller 2008).

Nitrogen content was low in general, because of the virgin soil covering the landscape, although available nitrogen was ranging from 33.5 mg.kg⁻¹ up to 119.1 mg.kg⁻¹. The highest values of nitrogen content refer to lands where their fields are under kind of management therefore it is exposed to fertilization and fertilizers as it will be mentioned below. Available phosphorus content was also low because of the nature of the calcareous soils and how they act on phosphorus fixation as insoluble compounds of phosphate (Helyar and Anderson 1971; Jensen *et al.*, 1998; Braschi *et al.*, 2003). Iraqi soils are considered to have enough amount of total and available potassium (Kanani *et al.*, 1989; Al-Zubaidi 2001), therefore we can see that the content of available potassium in soil was high when compared to other virgin soils. It ranged between 100-251 mg.kg⁻¹ where the highest contents were in coarser soil texture than the finer ones, and that's could be related to the common content of potassium feldspars in sand minerals (Sadusky *et al.*, 1987, Sparks 1986; Pal *et al.*, 2001) besides the fixation process of

potassium in clayey soils (Wear and White 1961; Inoue 1983; Simonson 2009).

These figures above shows that soil pH and Electrical conductivity were the least variable properties in the studied area, where first these areas are receiving more quantities of precipitation with lower annual temperature the matter that doesn't support salt accumulation in soil. Also from seeing pH and EC distribution, they look related to the role of decreasing pH values with the increase of salts in soil extracts. Organic matter showed another distribution where the highest content was related to the highest areas in elevation, precipitation, and temperature, and that it is related to the increase of litters and accumulation of OM in soil other than oxidizing it in other areas. Carbonate equivalent did not show trend distribution because of parent material of soils in the area of study is considered to be highly calcareous therefore, the distribution was not following a law.

Cation exchange capacity was related in its distribution to clay and sand content, and that could also be followed through table 1 and 2.

Coarser textured soils were the least in the studied area, followed by finer textured soil, while medium textured soils have they most extensive distribution in the area of study (figure 2). Nitrogen, phosphorus, and potassium were distributed randomly in the soils of northern Iraq. Low content of any property will definitely eliminate variability in it. Therefore, variation in available nitrogen was not as wide as phosphorus and potassium showed because nitrogen is exposed to leaching in a hand and volatilization in another hand (Stenberg *et al.*, 1999; Cameron *et al.*, 2013)

Spatial distribution and soil variability:

Figure (2) shows the spatial distribution of soil properties.

Fig. 2 : Spatial distribution of soil properties

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